

**A tutorial on
Creating a Polycrystalline Volume Element in DREAM.3D
and exporting to Finite Element Software**

DREAM.3D version 6.5.171

Download link: <http://dream3d.bluequartz.net>

Last Updated: January 2026

Dr. Himanshu Gupta

email: ghimanshu@iisc.ac.in

Department of Aerospace Engineering
Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-12

Welcome

This tutorial provides a step-by-step workflow to create a polycrystalline volume element using DREAM.3D, and to export the grain geometry as .STL files for subsequent finite element simulations

Problem statement

Generate a voxel-based synthetic polycrystalline volume element (PVE) of dimension of $1000 \times 100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^3$, composed of equiaxed grains with a mean grain size of $40 \mu\text{m}$ and random crystallographic orientations.

The generated microstructure should be suitable for export as grain-resolved .STL files that can be transferred to any finite element (FE) software for subsequent numerical analysis, i.e., wave propagation or mechanical simulations.

Requirements

PVE

- Dimension: 1000 x 100 x 100 μm^3
- Mean grain size: 40 μm
- Grain size distribution: Flexible (No constraint)
- Grain shape: Equiaxed
- Crystallographic orientation distribution: Random
- Grain orientation spread: No constraint

Part 1: Creating a pipeline in DREAM.3D
Version 6.5.171

Overall workflow: DREAM3D interface

Step 1: Filter selection StatsGenerator

1.1

Search for *StatsGenerator*
in the filter list

1.2

Double-click the selection

1.3

Click the selected filter
in the pipeline window

Step 1: Filter selection

StatsGenerator → Size Distribution

1.4

Select "Size Dist."

1.5

By default the mean grain size (or equivalent sphere diameter) is 2.73191 μm

Step 1: Filter selection

StatsGenerator → Size Distribution

1.6

Parameters to play with:

- (a) Mu
- (b) Sigma
- (c) Min/Max cut off
- (d) Bin Step Size

Requirement:
Mean GS*: $40 \mu\text{m}$

Vary Mu accordingly to get
Mean Feature ESD $\approx 40 \mu\text{m}$

No restrictions on others parameters

*GS: Grain Size

Step 1: Filter selection

StatsGenerator → Size Distribution

1.7

At Mu value: 3.683..
Mean Feature ESD
appears to be 40 μm

Meanwhile,
Min/Max Cut-off
decides the overall
GS distribution

Here:
Min GS: 32.58 μm
Max GS: 48.61 μm

Step 1: Filter selection

StatsGenerator → Grain Shape

1.8

Requirement:
Equiaxed grains

By default selection:
Primary equiaxed

Step 1: Filter selection

StatsGenerator → Grain Orientation

1.10

Select Orientation Distribution Function (ODF)

By default, DREAM.3D selects the random grain orientation

Requirement: Random orientation
Hence, no changes.

The screenshot shows the StatsGenerator software interface. At the top, the title bar reads "StatsGenerator". Below it, the "Parameters" section is visible. A horizontal menu contains several options: "Size Dist.", "Omega3", "B/A", "C/A", "Neighbor", "ODF", "MDF", and "Axis ODF". The "ODF" option is highlighted with a blue border. Below this menu, there are radio buttons for "Manual Entry" (selected) and "Bulk Load From File". A table with columns "Euler 1", "Euler 2", "Euler 3", "Weight", and "Sigma" is shown, with a "+" button to its left and an "x" button to its right. A text box with an arrow pointing to the "+" button contains the text "Click '+' for any preferred orientation". Below the table, the "Sample Points" is set to 5000. Three circular plots are displayed, labeled "<001>", "<011>", and "<111>". At the bottom, there are controls for "Image Size" (set to 200), "Image Layout" (set to Horizontal), and "Type" (set to Discrete). A text box with an arrow pointing to these controls contains the text "Refreshing the ODF". On the right side, there is a "Create Data" button and a "Reset..." button. A text box with an arrow pointing to the "Create Data" button contains the text "Click: Create Data". A green circle with the number "1.11" is located on the right side of the interface.

1.11

Step 2: Filter selection

Initialize Synthetic Volume

2.1

Search for *Initialize Synthetic Volume* in the filter list

2.2

Double-click the selection

2.3

Click the selected filter in the pipeline window

Step 2: Filter selection

Initialize Synthetic Volume

2.4

Check:
Estimate Number
of Features

This will tell the
approximate
number of grains
to be created
inside the PVE

2 Initialize Synthetic Volume

Parameters

Estimate Number of Features

Dimensions 128 128 128

Resolution 0.25 0.25 0.25

Origin 0 0 0

Box Size in Length Units X Range: 0 to 32 (Delta: 32)
Y Range: 0 to 32 (Delta: 32)
Z Range: 0 to 32 (Delta: 32)

Required Objects

Cell Ensemble Data

Statistics StatsGeneratorDataContainer / CellEnsembleData / Statistics

Created Objects

Synthetic Volume Data Container SyntheticVolumeDataContainer

Cell Data

Cell Attribute Matrix CellData

Ensemble Attribute Matrix CellEnsembleData

Step 2: Filter selection Initialize Synthetic Volume

2.5

Requirements:

PVE dimensions

1000 x 100 x 100 μm^3

(a)

1000 x 100 x 100

Voxel Resolution 1 x 1 x 1

(b)

100 x 10 x 10

Voxel Resolution 10 x 10 x 10

a

Parameters

Estimate Number of Features

Estimated Primary Features 298

Dimensions 1000 100 100

Resolution 1 1 1

Origin 0 0 0

b

Parameters

Estimate Number of Features

Estimated Primary Features 298

Dimensions 100 10 10

Resolution 10 10 10

Origin 0 0 0

Both cases will fulfil the requirement: The only difference is the computational memory consumption (a >> b)
Estimated number of features/grains: 298, i.e., approximate number of grains in the final PVE \approx 298

Step 2: Filter selection Initialize Synthetic Volume

Implications of voxel-resolution

2.5
a

Actual number of grains created: 351

2.5
b

Actual number of grains created: 340

Understanding dimension and voxel resolution entries

Question 1: Which of the following combinations will also give the same PVE dimension as required?

- (i) Dimension: 4000 x 400 x 400
Resolution: 0.25 x 0.25 x 0.25
- (ii) Dimension: 200 x 20 x 20
Resolution: 5 x 5 x 5
- (iii) Dimension: 10 x 1 x 1
Resolution: 100 x 100 x 100

Question 2: Arrange the above cases in order of memory consumption and time to run the pipeline?

Question 3: Can the voxel resolution be larger than the dimension entries? Yes/No?
What would be the physical implication of this?

Question 4: Which of the above cases would have a higher number of grains (i) or (ii),
Or would it be approximately equal?

Step 3: Filter selection Establish Shape Types

3.1

Search for *Establish Shape Types* in the filter list

3.2

Double-click the selection

3.3

Click the selected filter
in the pipeline window

Step 3: Filter selection Establish Shape Types

3.4

By default selection
on this window; no
changes

Read: DREAM.3D
manual for more
details

3 Establish Shape Types

Required Objects

Cell Ensemble Data

Phase Types StatsGeneratorDataContainer / CellEnsembleData / PhaseTypes

Phase Types: StatsGeneratorDataContainer/CellEnsembleData/PhaseTypes

Created Objects

Cell Ensemble Data

Shape Types ShapeTypes

Shape Types

Primary (1): Ellipsoid

Shape Types: Primary (1): Ellipsoid

Step 4: Filter selection Pack Primary Phases

4.1

Search for *Pack Primary Phases* in the filter list

4.2

Double-click the selection

4.3

Click the selected filter
in the pipeline window

Step 4: Filter selection

Pack Primary Phases

4.4

By default selection on this window; no changes

Read: DREAM.3D manual for more details

4 Pack Primary Phases

Parameters

Periodic Boundaries

Use Mask

Feature Generation ▼

Save Shape Description Arrays ▼

Required Objects

Cell Data

Cell Attribute Matrix

Cell Ensemble Data

Statistics

Phase Types

Phase Names

Shape Types

Created Objects

Cell Data

Feature Ids

Phases

Cell Feature Data

Cell Feature Attribute Matrix

Step 5: Filter selection

Find Feature Neighbors

5.1

Search for *Find Feature Neighbors* in the filter list

5.2

Double-click the selection

5.3

Click the selected filter in the pipeline window

Step 5: Filter selection

Find Feature Neighbors

5.4

Check:
Store Surface
Feature Array

It should
create an object:
SurfaceFeatures

5 Find Feature Neighbors

Parameters

- Store Boundary Cells Array
- Store Surface Features Array

Required Objects

Cell Data

Feature Ids

Cell Feature Data

Cell Feature Attribute Matrix

Created Objects

Cell Data

Cell Feature Data

Number of Neighbors

Neighbor List

Shared Surface Area List

Surface Features

Step 5: Filter selection Find Feature Neighbors

5.5

Right-click on
FeatureIds

5 Find Feature Neighbors i

Parameters

- Store Boundary Cells Array
- Store Surface Features Array

Required Objects

Cell Data

Feature Ids ImageDataContainer / CellData / FeatureIds

Cell Feature Data

Cell Feature Attribute Matrix ImageDataContainer / CellFeatureData

StatsGeneratorDataContainer

SyntheticVolumeDataContainer

- CellData
 - FeatureIds
- CellEnsembleData
 - Phases
- CellFeatureData

Created Objects

Cell Data

Cell Feature Data

Number of Neighbors

Neighbor List

Shared Surface Area List

Surface Features

Feature Ids: ImageDataContainer/CellData/FeatureIds

Step 5: Filter selection

Find Feature Neighbors

5.6

Right-click on
Cell Feature
Attribute Matrix

5 Find Feature Neighbors

Parameters

- Store Boundary Cells Array
- Store Surface Features Array

Required Objects

Cell Data

Feature Ids SyntheticVolumeDataContainer / CellData / FeatureIds

Cell Feature Data

Cell Feature Attribute Matrix ImageDataContainer / CellFeatureData

Created Objects

Cell Data

Cell Feature Data

Number of Neighbors NumNeighbors

Neighbor List NeighborList

Shared Surface Area List SharedSurfaceAreaList

Surface Features SurfaceFeatures

Cell Feature Attribute Matrix: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer/CellFeatureData

Step 6: Filter selection Match Crystallography

6.1

Search for *Match Crystallography*
in the filter list

6.2

Double-click the selection

6.3

Click the selected filter
in the pipeline window

Step 6: Filter selection

Match Crystallography

6.4

Change maximum number of iterations to a higher number say, 100000

No changes required in the rest of the sections

Read: DREAM.3D manual for more details

The screenshot shows the 'Match Crystallography' window with a title bar containing the number '6' and an information icon. The 'Parameters' section is highlighted with a blue border and a black arrow pointing to it from the left. The 'Maximum Number of Iterations (Swaps)' is set to '100000'. Below this are sections for 'Required Objects' and 'Created Objects', each containing various data fields and their corresponding paths.

Section	Object Name	Path
Required Objects	Cell Data	
	Feature Ids	SyntheticVolumeDataContainer / CellData / FeatureIds
	Cell Feature Data	
	Phases	SyntheticVolumeDataContainer / CellFeatureData / Phases
	Surface Features	SyntheticVolumeDataContainer / CellFeatureData / SurfaceFeatures
	Neighbor List	SyntheticVolumeDataContainer / CellFeatureData / NeighborList
	Shared Surface Area List	SyntheticVolumeDataContainer / CellFeatureData / SharedSurfaceAreaList
	Cell Ensemble Data	
	Statistics	StatsGeneratorDataContainer / CellEnsembleData / Statistics
	Crystal Structures	StatsGeneratorDataContainer / CellEnsembleData / CrystalStructures
Created Objects	Cell Data	
	Euler Angles	EulerAngles
	Cell Feature Data	
	Volumes	Volumes

Step 7: Filter selection Generate IPF Colors

7.1

Search for *Generate IPF Colors* in the filter list

7.2

Double-click the selection

7.3

Click the selected filter in the pipeline window

Step 7: Filter selection

Generate IPF Colors

7.4

Reference direction:
By default 0 0 1

7.5

Required objects entries are as follows:
By right-clicking on each entry:

7 Generate IPF Colors

Parameters

Reference Direction 0 0 1

Apply to Good Elements Only (Bad Elements Will Be Black)

Required Objects

Element Data

Euler Angles

Phases

Ensemble Data

Crystal Structures

Created Objects

Element Data

IPF Colors IPFColor

EulerAngles: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer/CellData/EulerAngle

Phases: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer/CellData/Phases

Crystal Structures: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer/CellEnsembleData/CrystalStructure

Step 7: Filter selection

Generate IPF Colors

7 Generate IPF Colors ⓘ

Parameters

Reference Direction

Apply to Good Elements Only (Bad Elements Will Be Black)

Required Objects

Element Data _____

Euler Angles

Phases

Ensemble Data _____

Crystal Structures

Created Objects

Element Data _____

IPF Colors

7.5

Updated entries
in the Required
Object section

Step 8: Filter selection

Write DREAM.3D Data File

8.1

Search for *Write DREAM.3D Data File* in the filter list

8.2

Double-click the selection

8.3

Click the selected filter in the pipeline window

Step 8: Filter selection

Write DREAM.3D Data File

8.4

Output File:
Choose a path
in a directory to
save the
DREAM.3D file

Step 9: Filter selection Quick Surface Mesh

9.1

Search for *Quick Surface Mesh*
in the filter list

9.2

Double-click the selection

9.3

Click the selected filter
in the pipeline window

Step 9: Filter selection Quick Surface Mesh

9.4

Right-click on
Feature Ids
&
Attribute Arrays to
Transfer

Make entries as
follows:

The screenshot shows the 'Quick Surface Mesh' interface. The 'Required Objects' section has the following fields:

- Cell Data: [Empty]
- Feature Ids: ImageDataContainer / CellData / FeatureIds
- Attribute Arrays to Transfer: [Empty]

Below these fields are two columns: 'Available Data Arrays' and 'Selected Data Arrays'. Two green callout boxes highlight the following entries:

- Feature Ids: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer/CellData/FeatureIds
- Attribute Arrays to Transfer: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer/CellData

The 'Created Objects' section has the following fields:

- Data Container: TriangleDataContainer
- Vertex Data: [Empty]
- Vertex Attribute Matrix: VertexData
- Node Types: NodeType
- Face Data: [Empty]
- Face Attribute Matrix: FaceData
- Face Labels: FaceLabels
- Face Feature Data: [Empty]
- Face Feature Attribute Matrix: FaceFeatureData

Step 10: Filter selection

Export STL Files from Triangle Geometry

10.1

Search for *Export STL Files From Triangle Geometry* in the filter list

10.2

Double-click the selection

10.3

Click the selected filter in the pipeline window

Step 10: Filter selection

Export STL Files from Triangle Geometry

10.4

Output STL Directory:
Choose a path to save the STL files of grains (a new folder)

10

Export STL Files from Triangle Geometry

Parameters

Output STL Directory

STL File Prefix

Required Objects

FaceData

FaceLabels

10.5

Provide a file prefix –
That will be added with each STL file
For example:
TutorialSTL_1
TutorialSTL_2
TutorialSTL_3 .. and so on
.. till the total number of grains

Step 11: Filter selection

Export Feature Data as CSV File

11.1

Search for *Export Feature Data as CSV File* in the filter list

11.2

Double-click the selection

11.3

Click the selected filter in the pipeline window

Step 11: Filter selection

Export Feature Data as CSV File

11.4

Output File:
Choose a path to save
the “Feature Data”
in a CSV file

Feature data, i.e.,
Euler angles information,
number of neighbouring
grains, etc.

11.5 Fill the “Required Object” entry as follows

Feature Attribute Matrix: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer/CellFeatureData

Step 12: Run Pipeline

12.

Click:
Start Pipeline

Pipeline

- 01 StatsGenerator
- 02 Initialize Synthetic Volume
- 03 Establish Shape Types
- 04 Pack Primary Phases
- 05 Find Feature Neighbors
- 06 Match Crystallography
- 07 Generate IPF Colors
- 08 Write DREAM.3D Data File
- 09 Quick Surface Mesh
- 10 Export STL Files from Triangle Ge...
- 11 Export Feature Data as CSV File

Export Feature Data as CSV File

Parameters

Output File: D:\OneDrive - Indian Institute of Science\G Drive\DREAM3D_Tutorial_Files\Tutorial_FeatureData_CSV_File.csv **Select...**

Write Neighbor Data

Write Number of Features Line

Delimiter: ,

Required Objects

Feature Data

Feature Attribute Matrix: SyntheticVolumeDataContainer / CellFeatureData

Data Structure

- StatsGeneratorDataContainer
 - CellEnsembleData
 - CrystalStructures
 - PhaseName
 - PhaseTypes
 - ShapeTypes
 - Statistics
 - SyntheticVolumeDataContainer
 - CellData
 - EulerAngles
 - FeatureIds
 - IPFColor
 - Phases

Filter List

- Export Feature Data as CSV File

Human Label (1)

- Export Feature Data as CSV File

Unique Filter Count: 1

Start Pipeline

Pipeline Output

```
Writing Feature Data || 60.2374% Complete
Writing Feature Data || 65.2819% Complete
Writing Feature Data || 70.0297% Complete
Writing Feature Data || 75.0742% Complete
Writing Feature Data || 80.1187% Complete
Writing Feature Data || 85.1632% Complete
Writing Feature Data || 90.2077% Complete
Writing Feature Data || 95.2522% Complete
Pipeline Complete
***** PIPELINE FINISHED *****
```

Part 2: Viewing the PVE in Paraview
Version 5.11.1

Step 13: Viewing the PVE in Paraview

13.1

Click: Open

13.2

Select the saved Xdmf file from the saved folder

File name:
“DREAM3D_Tutorial.xdmf”

Step 13: Viewing the PVE in Paraview

13.3

Select XDMF Reader

And click OK

Step 13: Viewing the PVE in Paraview

13.4

Click on “eye” icon
Click on “Apply”

Search “Map
Scalars” here
and uncheck it.

Step 13: Viewing the PVE in Paraview

13.5

Click: Outline dropdown and select "Surface"

Step 13: Viewing the PVE in Paraview

13.6

Click: Solid Color dropdown and select “IPFCOLOR”

Step 13: Viewing the PVE in Paraview

Final outcome:

Step 14: .STL files

Will get saved in the folder path
created in step 10.4

Name	Status	Date modified	Type	Size
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	File folder		
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	DREAM3D File	542 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	XDMF File	2 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	Microsoft Excel C...	31 KB	

Ready to transfer into FE software

Keep in mind:

- A practical limitation of this approach is that grain geometries are transferred to the finite element software individually (one-by-one).
- Which can be time-consuming for large polycrystalline volumes.
- Increasing the number of grains improves microstructural representation but also increases the manual effort required during FE model setup.

Name	Status	Date modified	Type	Size
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	10 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	411 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	7 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	11 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	10 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	6 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	7 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	7 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	11 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	8 KB	
R	28-Jan-26 2:05 AM	STL File	10 KB	

Step 15: Reading Feature Data .CSV file

Total number of feature/grains

Volume of voxels belonging to one grain

1 → Single phase grain

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
331											
Feature_ID	AvgQuats_0	AvgQuats_1	AvgQuats_2	AvgQuats_3	EulerAngles_0	EulerAngles_1	EulerAngles_2	NumNeighbors	Phases	SurfaceFeatures	Volumes
1	-0.3039353	0.45590058	0.41991815	0.7234962	4.7745099	1.1597638	0.45690706	9	1	1	43000
2	-0.028005	-0.5852127	-0.7558222	0.29236054	2.7246892	1.2519367	5.9619179	6	1	1	27000
3	0.56330907	-0.2795998	-0.2763595	0.72672713	3.0442586	1.3602301	3.9657092	13	1	1	42000
4	-0.180827	-0.6236464	0.40104553	0.64616501	0.73311514	1.413414	4.4391327	12	1	1	56000
5	0.04055604	-0.5964816	0.58571064	0.54727316	0.81937283	1.2816545	3.8251903	5	1	1	24000
6	-0.4857215	0.10489964	0.72349507	0.47919255	5.0846834	1.0400915	5.5100832	9	1	1	27000
7	-0.0218747	-0.6402556	0.05786082	0.76566738	1.4612181	1.3906345	4.6711154	11	1	1	29000
8	0.17984225	-0.1371926	0.68376893	0.69375432	1.7117687	0.45634326	3.0151176	11	1	1	49000
9	0.10277084	-0.6842292	-0.3681544	0.62107241	2.2549694	1.5282463	5.098392	10	1	1	34000
10	0.37361187	0.87966949	-0.2909291	0.04422652	3.3795326	1.3025268	2.1697237	16	1	0	41000

Serial number of each grain

AvgQuats_0, 1, 2, 3
Grain's orientation expressed in quaternion form

Euler angle (in rad) of every grain ($\varphi_1, \Phi, \varphi_2$)
Sufficient in calculating the stiffness matrices of a grain for FE simulations

Number of neighbouring grains

SurfaceFeature
1 → Grain touches the outer surface of the PVE
0 → Grain completely inside the PVE

Suggested Reading Materials:

- [1]. M. A. Groeber and M. A. Jackson, “Dream.3d: A digital representation environment for the analysis of microstructure in 3d,” Integrating Materials and Manufacturing Innovation, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 56–72, Apr. 2014. doi: 10.1186/2193-9772-3-5
- [2]. DREAM.3D reference manual. Link: <https://dream3d.bluequartz.net/Help/>
- [3]. H. Gupta, S. Gopalakrishnan, and S. Suwas, “Elastic wave propagation in textured polycrystalline materials: A computationally-efficient and experimentally-supported approach,” *Materialia*, vol. 102465, 2025, doi:10.1016/j.mtla.2025.102465.

Acknowledgement:

I sincerely thank **Michael Jackson** (Lead Developer of DREAM.3D) for the guidance and discussions that were extremely helpful during my learning, and for kindly reviewing this tutorial.

I hope this tutorial is helpful to readers.

For any questions, clarifications, or feedback, please feel free to contact me.

All the best

